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THE QUALITY OF LIQUID FUELS OFFERED IN THE TRADE NETWORK OF POPOVO CITY, BULGARIA

Mihova M.,

Bachelor of Economics

Specialty "Commodity Science and Customs Activity"

University of Economics,

Varna, Bulgaria

Radev R.

Doctor of Commodity Science, Chief Assistant Professor

University of Economics

Varna, Bulgaria

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to study the quality of liquid fuels offered in the trade network of Popovo city, Bulgaria. The color of liquid fuels is inherent and characteristic, but different hues are observed in motor gasolines, probably due to the presence of artificial additives, dissolved resins or ethyl liquids. The diesel fuels sold from „B“, „C“ and „E“ are cloudy and they are found to have comparatively lower mobility than the others. The presence of opalescence or the content of mechanical impurities in gasoline and diesel fuels is not observed. Gasoline samples taken from „E“ and „D“ are substandard due to their increased density. The diesel fuels offered by „A“, „D“ and „E“ are non-standard, due to their density not being consistent with the standardized norms. The obtained flame temperature of the diesel fuels is in accordance with the regulatory requirements. Gasoline and diesel fuels do not contain water-soluble acids and bases, with the exception of „E“ brand diesel fuel.

Keywords: quality, liquid fuels, quality of liquid fuels.

Introduction

In the context of the growing requirements for fuels, including those related to their impact on the environment, the question of the quality of liquid fuels is becoming more and more relevant. The quality of liquid fuels is the subject of compliance between their quality indicators in relation to standard requirements. The fuels that are produced and offered on the market in Bulgaria must meet the standards adopted in the European Union, which set stricter requirements than the previously existing national standards until the country's accession to the EU [1].

The quality of liquid fuels is one of the key factors that have an impact on engine performance. Particular attention when updating quality standards is paid to the environmental characteristics of fuels, including properties such as sulfur content, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and other pollutants found in diesel and gasoline. The entire set of properties of liquid fuels that determine their quality can be divided into three groups - physico-chemical, operational and technical. Physical and chemical properties characterize the state of liquid

fuels and their composition (density, viscosity, heat capacity, thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity, fractional composition, etc.). The second group contains all operational properties of liquid fuels that ensure the reliability and efficiency of the operation of engines, machines and mechanisms, such as the octane/cetane number of liquid fuels. The technical properties of liquid fuels are combined in a third group. They are not related to their use, but are manifested in the processes of storage and transportation, such as flame and ignition temperature. These fuel quality requirements are subject to analysis and testing in petrochemical laboratories and are determined to be the most important in terms of vehicle engine performance and durability, as well as emissions [1,2,3,4].

The evaluation of the quality is done by comparing the values of the quality indicators of the liquid fuels with base values from the regulated normative requirements. In the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and manner of their control are reflected in tables that note the indicators necessary to assess the level of quality of the tested products, the reference values that they must

meet and the methods for testing them accordingly generally accepted international standards [5].

Gasoline is a mixture of liquid, paraffinic, naphthenic and aromatic hydrocarbons. It is a clear to slightly yellowish, transparent, easily mobile liquid, insoluble in water and lighter than it. It has a specific smell, and depending on the octane number, it can have a different color. The density of gasoline at 15°C is 720-775 kg/m³. The content of water-soluble acids and bases in gasoline is not allowed. *Motor gasoline* is used as a fuel for car and motorcycle engines. It is obtained during atmospheric distillation of oil, during thermal or catalytic cracking or, most often, when mixing gasoline obtained in all three ways. The fuel obtained by direct

distillation consists mainly of saturated hydrocarbons (hexane, cyclohexane and cyclopentane) and contains more hydrogen. It is characterized by a high octane number and detonation resistance. Gasoline obtained through the cracking process contains a larger amount of indefinite and aromatic hydrocarbons, and its chemical composition depends on the properties of the crude oil in the conditions under which cracking is produced [6,7].

Table 1 reflects the quality indicators for motor gasoline according to the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, which will be used for the purposes of this scientific article.

Table 1

Quality indicators of automobile gasoline

Indicators	Requirements	
	Minimum	Maximum
1. Appearance	Clear and bright liquid	
2. Density at 15°C, in kg/m ³	720,0	775,0
3. Water soluble acids and bases	Absence	

Sources: Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, amended. and add. DV. No. 63 of July 31, 2018 [5]

Diesel is a slightly mobile liquid with an orange-brown color, and its density varies in the range of 820 - 845 kg/m³. Good quality fuel must have a flash point of at least 55°C and not contain water-soluble acids and bases. Diesel fuels are liquid fuels for diesel engines (automotive, tractor, marine) in which ignition takes place without a side source of ignition. Fresh air is drawn into the engine cylinders, which is highly compressed and, as a result, heated to a high temperature. The fuel is atomized in the heated air, the vapor-air mixture formed self-ignites and burns completely [8].

Diesel fuel is obtained by atmospheric distillation of oil in a temperature range from 270°C to 360°C. Most often, motor diesel fuel is produced by mixing distillate fractions from secondary and primary oil processing, with the addition of various additives [8].

Table 2 reflects the quality indicators of fuel for diesel engines according to the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, which are studied in this article.

Table 2

Quality indicators of fuels for diesel engines

Indicators	Requirements	
	Minimum	Maximum
1. Density at 15°C, in kg/m ³	820,0	845,0
2. Ignition temperature of fuel	Above 55°C	—
3. Water-soluble acids and bases	Absence	

Sources: Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, amended. and add. DV. No. 63 of July 31, 2018 [5]

The purpose of this article is to study the quality of liquid fuels offered in the trade network of Popovo city, Bulgaria.

Methodology and data

To achieve the scientific goal in this article are used: descriptive-analytical method, study of various scientific literature, Bulgarian regulations, systematic approach, comparative analysis, statistics, method of observation, induction, deduction, etc..

For the purposes of the scientific research, 5 samples of automobile gasoline (A – 95H) and 5 samples of diesel fuel were procured. The experimental samples have a capacity of 1 l and were taken according to the number of functioning commercial brands of gas stations in the territory of Popovo, Bulgaria. For the purpose of the study, the samples have conventional names „A“, „B“, „C“, „D“ and „E“.

The testing of the liquid fuels was carried out three times in the Research Laboratory at the Department of "Commodity Science" at the University of economics - Varna, in the month of May 2022.

Methods used

Organoleptic and instrumental methods were used to study the quality of liquid fuels. *The organoleptic method* is based on information obtained by using the natural perceptions of the human sense organs: sight, hearing, smell, etc. The reliability of the assessment by this method is highly dependent on the training and sensory perceptions of the assessor. *The instrumental method* is based on the use of technical means to determine the values of the quality indicators. It provides the highest accuracy and objectivity [9, 10].

Sensory methods for determining the quality indicators of liquid fuels

✓ Determining the appearance and color of liquid fuels

Appearance and color are determined by pouring a small amount of the liquid fuels into a test tube and visually assessing scattered light. Evaluated: fuel mobility, color, transparency, presence of opalescence and content of mechanical impurities in the fuel [11].

Instrumental methods for determining the quality indicators of liquid fuels

✓ Determination of density of liquid fuels

Density is the mass of a liquid divided by its volume at 15°C or 20°C, expressed in units of mass and volume, taking into account the reference temperature (g/cm^3 at 15°C). If the measurement was performed at a different temperature, it is necessary to make a temperature correction [12].

An analytical balance and a beaker with a capacity of at least 250 ml are required for the test. A beaker is

placed on the analytical balance into which, after resetting the scale, 200 ml of the tested sample is poured. To obtain the final result, the value that is written on the display of the scale is multiplied by 5. This mathematical equation is necessary, because according to a regulatory document, the unit of measurement is kg/m^3 , and at the same time, the available fuel sample is the same amount.

✓ Determination of ignition temperature of liquid fuels

The ignition temperature is the temperature at which fuel vapors, heated under standard conditions, form with the surrounding air a combustible mixture capable of igniting when exposed to fire. It can be used to judge the temperature conditions of storage of liquid fuels, which should be observed in order to avoid the formation of an ignitable mixture [12].

For determine the ignition temperature, a Marcuson apparatus (Figure 1) with an open crucible, a mercury thermometer up to 400°C and a device for introducing a flame was used [12].

Figure 1. Marcuson apparatus

The tested fuel is poured into the well-dried crucible of the apparatus. On the inside of the crucible are drawn 2 lines - red and black. At an expected ignition temperature of up to 250°C, the crucible is filled to the black line, and at an expected ignition temperature above 250°C – to the red line. The full crucible is placed in the socket of the apparatus. A mercury thermometer is placed in the sample in a vertical position using a special device holder. The heating of the sample is carried out using a built-in electric heater and an additional device for regulating the rate of temperature rise. The reading of the thermometer at the moment of the first ignition of the vapors of the product, at which a faint crackling is also heard, is taken as the ignition temperature [12].

✓ Determining the content of water-soluble acids and bases in liquid fuels

Water-soluble acids and bases are an undesirable ingredient in liquid fuels because they can cause corrosion of metal storage vessels, mechanisms, and engines [12].

50 cm³ of the liquid fuel and 50 cm³ of distilled water, preheated to 50-60°C, are placed in a separatory funnel. The contents of the separatory funnel were homogenized by shaking for 5 minutes, taking care not to form an emulsion. After separation, the lower aqueous layer was discharged into a conical flask through a filter paper funnel and cooled to room temperature [12].

From 1 to 10 cm³ of the extract is placed in three test tubes, and the same volume of distilled water is

poured into two other test tubes. They are used as controls to compare the color of the metal orange and methyl rot indicators [12].

In one of the test tubes, add 2 drops of methyl orange solution. The pink coloring of the extract indicates the presence of water-soluble acids in the liquid fuel being tested. In the second test tube with a scoop, add 2 drops of methyl rot. The pink coloring of the extract indicates the presence of water-soluble acids in the test fuel. The tubes can be compared to control samples in which the same indicators have been added. In the third test tube, add 3 packets of phenolphthalein solution. The pink coloring of the solution indicates the presence of water-soluble bases [12].

It is assumed that the liquid fuel does not contain water-soluble acids and bases, in the absence of pink or red coloring of the extract from the indicators methyl orange, methyl rot and phenolphthalein [12].

Results and discussion

Study of the assortment of liquid fuels offered in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria in the period april - june 2022.

The production of liquid fuels and their sale in Bulgaria covers several stages along the chain of production/import - end user. Fuels reach from the producer or importer to the end users through distribution channels segmented into several separate levels. Through them, the faster, reliable and economically profitable reaching of the produced products to the sphere of consumption is realized [13].

Basically, the liquid fuels market can be analyzed by dividing it into four vertically related main components as follows:

- **Oil exploration and production** – refers to the exploration, extraction of crude oil and its transportation to where it is refined or processed.

- **Refining or importing motor fuel** - refers to the refining of crude oil to produce gasoline or diesel fuel, the blending of semi-refined feedstock and fuel components, or the import/intra-Community receipt of fuels from abroad.

- **Wholesale sales and transportation of large volumes of refined products** - as a result, refined products are transported to tax warehouses that perform the function of a distribution terminal. Transportation from refineries to secondary storage facilities can be accomplished by ship tankers, pipelines, road tankers, and rail

tankers. Large traders may resell part of their purchases to distributors, to retailers (gas stations) or industrial customers (factories, farmers, transport companies) or government departments. This is the second level of distribution and usually involves smaller quantities compared to refinery sales. Refined products are transported to customers (wholesalers or retailers) most often by road tankers.

- **Retail** - refers to sales at gas stations to end customers. Gas stations can be categorized into three main types:

- gas stations that sell under the brand name of companies traditionally involved in oil extraction and/or processing;
- independent gas stations;
- those that sell under the trademark of large gas station chains [13].

At the level of retail sales, in the town of Popovo, Bulgaria, the fuel trade is mainly carried out by companies that own small chains of gas stations, whose activity extends to neighboring regional towns, but there are also independent gas stations whose activity is concentrated in a single commercial establishment on the territory of the city. These are 5 companies with conventional names: „A“, „B“, „C“, D and E. An exception should be made for the sites trading in liquid fuels under the „E“ logo due to the fact that this is a company with one of the most developed networks from gas stations in the country and at the same time it is an established trademark with an established image.

Study of the commodity assortment of liquid fuels offered in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria

The market of liquid fuels in the territory of the town of Popovo is limited and uniform, being characterized by the sale of A-95H motor gasoline, ordinary diesel motor fuel and propane-butane gas. Only the gas station of "E" offers variety in the product assortment, providing end users with the opportunity to purchase fuel produced from biological resources, other than oil - biodiesel. A study was made of the stock assortment of liquid fuels during the period April – June 2022, and the data are presented in table 3, table 4 and table 5.

Table 3 shows the assortment of liquid fuels from different companies, offered to consumers in the commercial network of Popovo, Bulgaria for the month of april.

Table 3

Assortment of liquid fuels for the month of april

No	Companies	Assortment of liquid fuels			
		Gasoline A-95 H	Diesel	Propane-butane gas	Biodiesel
1	A	✓	✓	✓	-
2	B	✓	✓	✓	-
3	C	✓	✓	✓	-
4	D	✓	✓	✓	-
5	E	✓	✓	✓	✓

Source: Own research

According to the survey carried out in April, there are four types of liquid fuels that are available in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria -

motor gasoline A - 95H, diesel fuel, liquefied gas propane - butane and biodiesel, the last fuel being available only in the network on „E“.

Table 4 presents the assortment of liquid fuels from different companies, offered to consumers in the

commercial network of Popovo, Bulgaria for the month of May.

Table 4

Assortment of liquid fuels for the month of may

No	Companies	Assortment of liquid fuels			
		Gasoline A-95 H	Diesel	Propane-butane gas	Biodiesel
1	A	✓	✓	✓	-
2	B	✓	✓	✓	-
3	C	✓	✓	✓	-
4	D	✓	✓	✓	-
5	E	✓	✓	✓	✓

Source: Own research

According to the survey carried out in may, the assortment of liquid fuels offered in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria remains unchanged, with four types of liquid fuel again available - motor gasoline A - 95H, diesel fuel, liquefied propane

gas - butane and biodiesel, which is also offered this month only by „E”.

Table 5 presents the assortment of liquid fuels from different companies offered to consumers in the commercial network of Popovo, Bulgaria for the month of June.

Table 5

Assortment of liquid fuels for the month of June

No	Companies	Assortment of liquid fuels			
		Gasoline A-95 H	Diesel	Propane-butane gas	Biodiesel
1	A	✓	✓	✓	-
2	B	✓	✓	✓	-
3	C	✓	✓	✓	-
4	D	✓	✓	✓	-
5	E	✓	✓	✓	✓

Source: Own research

According to the survey carried out in June, liquid fuels that are available in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria remain the same as in the previous two months - motor gasoline A - 95H, diesel fuel, liquefied propane - butane gas and biodiesel, which does not available nowhere else but at „E”.

Therefore, during the period of research of the product range - April - June 2022, an unchanged supply of the types of liquid fuels was established in the commercial network of the town of Popovo, Bulgaria.

Study of the quality of liquid fuels offered in the commercial network of the city of Popovo, Bulgaria

Study of the quality of automobile gasoline A - 95H and diesel fuels according to organoleptic indicators

Automotive gasoline must be a light, transparent liquid, with a yellowish color, without the presence of mechanical impurities, opalescence. High-quality diesel, on the other hand, should have the same characteristics as gasoline, with the difference that its color should be orange-brown.

✓ Organoleptic indicators for the quality of automobile gasoline A - 95H

Sensory characteristics for different brands of automobile gasoline are divided into several tables, depending on the type of the studied indicator.

Table 6 shows the color of individual brands of fuel.

Table 6

Study of automobile gasolines A - 95H according to the indicator color

No	Company	Color
1	A	Slightly yellow
2	B	Straw yellow
3	C	Lemon yellow
4	D	Yellow
5	E	Deep amber

Source: Own research

The color of the individual types of motor gasoline is standard, and a characteristic yellow tint has been found, but different shades are observed in the liquid fuels studied. Gasoline sold under the „E” brand stands out the most from the others due to its rich amber color, while the fuel sold under the „A” brand has the most

inconspicuous coloring compared to the others. The reason for the different shades in the color may be the additives added to the fuel aimed at improving its quality.

Table 7 shows the transparency of individual types of automotive gasoline.

Table 7

Study of automobile gasolines A - 95H according to the indicator transparency

No	Company	Transparency
1	A	Transparent
2	B	Transparent
3	C	Transparent
4	D	Transparent
5	E	Transparent

Source: Own research

The tested samples comply with the requirement to be transparent. They are clear, crisp and not cloudy.

Table 8 shows the mobility of individual brands of automotive gasoline.

Table 8

Study of the mobility of automobile gasolines A - 95H

No	Company	Mobility
1	A	Strong mobility
2	B	Strong mobility
3	C	Strong mobility
4	D	Strong mobility
5	E	Strong mobility

Source: Own research

When the test tubes are shaken, easy mobility of the different types of liquid fuels is observed.

Table 9 notes the presence of mechanical impurities and opalescence in automotive gasolines.

Table 9

Content of mechanical impurities and opalescence in motor gasolines

No	Company	Opalescence	Mechanical impurities
1	A	Absence	Absence
2	B	Absence	Absence
3	C	Absence	Absence
4	D	Absence	Absence
5	E	Absence	Absence

Source: Own research

During the study, no presence of opalescence or mechanical impurities was found in the individual types of motor gasoline.

After the test, it was found that the samples met the requirements. They are transparent, mobile liquids, without the content of opalescence or mechanical impurities in them, with a characteristic yellow tint, but different shades in the color of individual brands of fuel are observed. A probable reason for this is the amount of gasoline additives used.

Modern engines require gasoline with a high octane number, and after distillation of the oil, pure gasoline has an octane number of about 60. The desired number is reached with the help of anti-knock additives, such as ethanol, naphthalene, ferrocene, methyl

butyl ether, metacyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl, etc. They differ not only in composition, but also in color. For example, metacyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl is yellow in color, while ferrocene is an orange powder, which accounts for the different hues in gasoline coloring [14, 15].

✓ Organoleptic indicators for quality of diesel fuels

Sensory characteristics for different brands of diesel fuel are divided into several tables, depending on the type of indicator studied.

Table 10 shows the color of the individual brands of diesel fuel.

Table 10

Study of diesel fuels according to the indicator color

No	Company	Color
1	A	Orange
2	B	Orange with brown undertones
3	C	Orange with brown undertones
4	D	Orange
5	E	Orange with brown undertones

Source: Own research

In the study, it was found that all the samples have a characteristic color and no uncharacteristic hues were observed in the diesel fuels.

Table 11 shows the transparency of individual brands of diesel fuel.

Table 11

Study of diesel fuels according to the indicator transparency

No	Company	Transparency
1	A	Transparent
2	B	Non transparent
3	C	Non transparent
4	D	Transparent
5	E	Non transparent

Source: Own research

Diesel fuels offered by companies „B“, „C“ and „E“ are non-standard in terms of the transparency requirement, being cloudy and opaque. A probable reason for this may be the additives added to the liquid fuels. Only fuels sold by „D“ and „A“ comply with this requirement.

Table 12 shows the mobility of individual brands of diesel fuel.

Table 12

Study of the mobility of diesel fuels

No	Company	Mobility
1	A	Movable
2	B	Poor mobility
3	C	Poor mobility
4	D	Movable
5	E	Poor mobility

Source: Own research

There is a correlation between the transparency of liquid fuels and their mobility, since diesel fuels that are found to be opaque also have comparatively lower mobility than the others. A probable reason for this could be the amounts of additives in liquid fuels.

Table 13 shows the content of opalescence and mechanical impurities in the individual brands of diesel fuel.

Table 13

Content of mechanical impurities and opalescence in diesel fuels

No	Company	Opalescence	Mechanical impurities
1	A	Absence	Absence
2	B	Absence	Absence
3	C	Absence	Absence
4	D	Absence	Absence
5	E	Absence	Absence

Source: Own research

After the study, it was found that there was no presence of opalescence or the content of mechanical impurities in the different brands of diesel fuel.

The sensory characteristics of diesel fuels are done analogously to that of automobile gasolines, and the quality indicators and requirements for them are identical and do not change. The tested diesel fuel samples have a characteristic color for their type and do not have mechanical impurities or opalescence. However, there is a deviation in the requirement for transparency of the diesels offered by the companies „B“, „C“ and „E“, as the same fuels are cloudy, opaque and with a comparatively lower mobility than the others. The reason for

this can be the additives added to the fuel aimed at optimizing the operation of diesel engines and other mechanisms in cars.

Instrumental indicators for the quality of automobile gasoline A - 95H and diesel fuel

Instrumental indicators for the quality of automobile gasoline A - 95H

✓ Density of automotive gasolines

The density of gasoline at 15°C according to the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control should be in the range of 720 - 775 kg/m³. The results of the laboratory tests on the relevant indicator are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14

Density of automotive gasolines

No	Company	Density /720 – 775 kg/m ³ /	Characteristic
1	A	756,28	Standard
2	B	749,80	Standard
3	C	755,85	Standard
4	D	778,95	Non-standard
5	E	785,52	Non-standard

Source: Own research

During the conducted research, it was established that the gasolines offered by „E“ and „D“ exceed the upper standard limit for the density indicator and are substandard. The reasons for this can be explained by the technological methods of processing the raw material (oil) or by adding special additives to the fuel that affect the density of gasoline. Gasoline fuels offered by companies „A“, „B“ and „C“ are standard in terms of

the same indicator, as their density meets the requirements in regulatory documents.

✓ **Content of water-soluble acids and bases in motor gasolines**

The content of water-soluble acids and bases in liquid fuels is undesirable, as they can cause corrosion of metal storage vessels, mechanisms, engines.

Table 15 shows the content of water-soluble acids and bases in motor gasoline.

Table 15

Content of water-soluble acids and bases in motor gasolines

No	Company	Water soluble acids and bases
1	A	Absence
2	B	Absence
3	C	Absence
4	D	Absence
5	E	Absence

Source: Own research

During the laboratory analysis, no amounts of water-soluble acids and bases were reported in the five samples of motor gasoline, therefore they are standard.

Instrumental quality indicators of diesel fuels

✓ **Density of diesel fuels**

The density of diesel fuels is noted in regulatory documents identical to automobile gasoline. The difference is in the values, which vary between 820 - 845 kg/m³, therefore diesel fuels have a higher density than gasoline.

Table 16 shows the density of different brands of diesel fuel.

Table 16

Study of diesel fuels according to the indicator density

No	Company	Density /820 – 845 kg/m ³ /	Characteristic
1	A	862,83	Non-standard
2	B	823,25	Standard
3	C	824,80	Standard
4	D	863,45	Non-standard
5	E	815,16	Non-standard

Source: Own research

During the research, it was found that the diesel fuels sold by „A“ and „E“, „D“ are non-standard, with the density of the first fuel below reference values for density, and the last two types of fuel - with values above the upper limit, described in the regulatory document. The high density of the fuel indicates the presence of heavier fractions in it.

✓ **Determination of ignition temperature of diesel fuels**

A flash point is determined only for diesel fuels. According to the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, it must be no less than 55°C.

Table 17 shows the values obtained from the mercury thermometer when determining the ignition temperature.

Table 17

Ignition temperature of diesel fuels

No	Company	Ignition temperature
1	A	64°C
2	B	59°C
3	C	68°C
4	D	65°C
5	E	70°C

Source: Own research

During the conducted research, it was established that all diesel fuel samples have a ignition point above 55°C, from which it follows that they are standard.

✓ **Content of water-soluble acids and bases in diesel fuels**

Both motor gasoline and diesel fuel should not contain water-soluble acids and bases.

Table 18 shows the content of water-soluble acids and bases in diesel fuels.

Table 18

Content of water-soluble acids and bases in diesel fuels

No	Company	Water soluble acids and bases
1	A	Absence
2	B	Absence
3	C	Absence
4	D	Absence
5	E	Pale pink coloration

Source: Own research

When conducting the laboratory analysis, only in the „E“ sample, when phenolphthalein was added to the product extract, a faint, barely perceptible pink coloration was produced in the test tube, which is evidence of the presence of water-soluble bases.

The quality of liquid fuels is carried out according to the compliance of their quality indicators with the standard requirements and the Ordinance on the requirements and quality of liquid fuels, the conditions and the order and method of their control. The following indicators were determined experimentally: density, ignition temperature and content of water-soluble acids and bases [12].

After the research done on the quality of liquid fuels offered in the city of Popovo, Bulgaria, it was

found that gasoline and diesel fuels do not contain water-soluble acids and bases. An exception should be made for "E" brand diesel fuel, as a pale pink coloration was found in the extract of the product when phenolphthalein was added. The obtained ignition temperature of the diesel fuels is in accordance with the regulatory requirements. The density of some gasoline and diesel samples does not correspond to the values in the standardized documents. Of the gasoline, the samples taken from „D“ and „E“ have a density whose value exceeds the standard limit, and of the diesel fuels, the samples taken from the companies „A“, „D“ and „E“ were found to be non-standard.

The obtained results are presented in table 19 and table 20.

Table 19

Determining the quality of automotive gasoline

No	Company	Density 720 – 775 kg/m ³	Content of water-soluble acids and bases /Absence/	Conclusion of quality
1.	A	756,28	Absence	Standard
2.	B	749,80	Absence	Standard
3.	C	755,85	Absence	Standard
4.	D	778,95	Absence	Non-standard
5.	E	785,52	Absence	Non-standard

Source: Own research

After the research, the motor gasolines offered by the companies „E“ and „D“ were found to be non-standard samples, as they are characterized by increased values according to the density indicator. A

probable reason for this is the addition of various gasoline additives to the fuel.

Determining the quality of diesel fuels

No	Company	Density /820 – 845 kg/m ³ /	Content of water-soluble acids and bases /Absence/	Ignition temperature /Over 55°C/	Conclusion of quality
1.	A	862,83	Absence	64°C	Non-standard
2.	B	823,25	Absence	59°C	Standard
3.	C	824,80	Absence	68°C	Standard
4.	D	863,45	Absence	65°C	Non-standard
5.	E	815,16	Presence	70°C	Non-standard

Source: Own research

The diesel fuels offered by „A“, „D“ and „E“ are non-standard because the density of the first fuel is below the reference values for the relevant indicator, and that of the last two types of fuel is high. The high density of the fuel indicates the presence of heavier fractions in it, which have a negative effect on the operation of the diesel engine, since the processes of volatility and dispersion in the combustion chamber of the internal combustion engine worsen. It is important to note that the density of diesel fuels depends on the temperature and season for which they are intended. Winter diesel has a lower density than summer diesel, as this prevents the fuel from solidifying at sub-zero temperatures. This gives, in effect, a potential explanation for the low density of the fuel sold by „E“. A probable reason is that at the time of sampling (month of May), the same company was still offering winter diesel fuel, which is in violation of the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and method of their control, according to which winter diesel fuel is available on the market from October 16th to April 15th, and summer fuel is available from April 16th to October 15th.

In addition, in the attempts to prove the presence of water-soluble acids and bases made with the „E“ diesel fuel, a slight pale pink coloration was found in the extract of the product, which established the presence of bases in the composition of the tested sample.

Conclusion

After the research carried out, it was found that the color of liquid fuels is inherent and characteristic, but different hues are observed in motor gasolines, probably due to the presence of artificial additives, dissolved resins or ethyl liquids. Almost all liquid fuel samples are clear, with the exception of diesel fuels sold from „B“, „C“ and „E“, which are cloudy. Cloudy diesel fuels offered by „B“, „C“ and „E“ are found to have comparatively lower mobility than the others. The presence of opalescence or the content of mechanical impurities in gasoline and diesel fuels is not observed. Gasoline samples taken from „E“ and „D“ are substandard due to their increased density. The diesel fuels offered by „A“, „D“ and „E“ are non-standard, due to their density not being consistent with the standardized norms. The obtained flame temperature of the diesel fuels is in accordance with the regulatory requirements. Gasoline and diesel fuels do not contain water-soluble acids and bases, with the exception of „E“ brand diesel fuel.

It would be good to implement a stricter internal company control, responsible for the quality of the supplied batches of liquid fuels, as well as more frequent

factual and documentary checks by the relevant control authorities, in order to maintain the quality of the products offered and protect of car engines.

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